

Preliminary exploration of the passport concept for the case of gelatin

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In this preliminary exploration, we describe potential elements that could be part of a so-called passport concept for materials, devices and systems. We use the material *gelatin* as an example and particularly focus on its inclusion as a gel in ECG electrode pads as a potential replacement for conventional gels.

Gelatin

Gelatin is a mixture of tasteless animal proteins. It is obtained from collagen, which is produced from the connective tissue of animals, mainly cows and pigs. Its main property is the sol-gel-transition: Above a transition temperature around 30°C, it dissolves, but when cooling down, it becomes a gel. Furthermore, it swells in water. This can be used to form a hydrogel from gelatin by cooling an aqueous gelatin solution from above the transition temperature down to room temperature (Lee et al., 2020).

Technology Performance

Conductivity

An important property of gels in ECG electrode pads is their high ionic conductivity. This is necessary because the electrical signals from the body should be transmitted to the measuring device with as little loss as possible, thus enabling a high signal-to-noise ratio (impedance matching). Gelatin itself has a low electronic conductivity. However, it can be doped with various conductive materials, such as PEDOT:PSS (Lee et al., 2020), metallic nanowires or carbon nanoparticles (Wang et al., 2022). Therefore, we see that gelatin as a pure material does not perform well in terms of conductivity. However, this problem can be solved by adding other materials. The question remains whether these materials will perform well in terms of biodegradability, which is the focus for this part of our exploration on electrode pads.

Flexibility

As the electrode will be placed on the patient's body, it should be highly flexible. Optimally, Young's modulus is similar to that of skin. However, skin is an anisotropic material, and so this value highly depends on the specific position of the body. Values between 25 kPa and 140 Mpa are typical for both tensile and torsion tests (Kalra et al., 2016). Therefore, this is not a well-defined criterion. For gelatin, good mechanical properties in terms of flexibility are observed (Lee et al., 2020). However, few authors also add other materials to improve the flexibility further. Nanowires are an example, which were used to reinforce the gel (Wang et al., 2022).

Cost-effectiveness

Commercial ECG electrode pads are mostly used once and disposed afterwards. Therefore, in order to compete with the electrodes already existing on the market, the components including the gel should be as cost-effective as possible. Gelatin is a waste product of the food industry. Therefore, it is highly cost effective and already widely used in many applications such as hydrogels. It is estimated that the market size of gelatin will reach 5 billion USD in 2025 (Alipal et al., 2021).

Compatibility

The gel is used in the ECG electrode along with other materials and therefore needs to be compatible with these materials. For the ECG electrode, these are mainly the substrate and the Ag/AgCl electrode. It is important to check that there are no unwanted chemical reactions at the interface. Since these are specific interactions, further experiments are needed. In addition, the contact between the gel and the Ag/AgCl electrode should be high enough so that the conductivity is not limited by this contact. Adhesion to the other parts can be obtained by incorporating the gelatin into the electrode in its liquid state and then cooling it to its gel state. This process yields good results in Lee et al. (2020).

Complexity of Reaction

Gelatin is produced mainly from animal parts like bones, hides, and skin. The production process involves pretreatment of raw material, extraction, purification, and gelatin production. Although the production involves numerous process steps, since industrial production began in 1850, there is sufficient experience to consider that the reaction is not particularly complex in the current technological era (Poppe, 1992).

Sustainability Performance

As part of the passport concept, we aim to explore environmental, social as well as economic performance while at the same time being conscious on how accessibility and use of these indicators can facilitate the inclusion of sustainability performance at the research level. The listed indicators are an initial starting point to explore this further. We also recognize that different materials, devices and systems require a focus on different elements of environmental, social and economic performance. Furthermore, we are aware that most approaches, as we do in this preliminary exploration, require a comparison to the state of the art. Future exploration aim to consider other approaches, for example setting a potential contribution to sustainability in the context of macro-level frameworks such as the planetary boundaries, to explore options on how to assess the sustainability performance from novel perspectives.

Environmental Sustainability Performance

When quantitative values are provided, these values are compared against Sodium Polyacrylate, a gel that is a current material used in commercial electrodes. All the impact values mentioned are the outcome of producing 1kg gelatin. Since the information is gathered from literature, variations in terms of quality of gelatin produced, the methodologies used to measure environmental impacts, etc., prevail. Simple comparisons among different literature might lead to false conclusions. However, for this exploratory work, we compared environmental impacts of gelatin assessed in two

articles 1) Gelatin produced from bone (Ma et al., 2019) and 2) Gelatin produced from fish wastes (Sampaio et al, 2017). Environmental data for Sodium Polyacrylate is referred from Gontia and Janssen (2016). The impact assessment methods for evaluating life cycle inventory data are different in all these studies. Variations among life cycle impact assessment methods, units used, and their inconsistencies were briefly discussed in Dong et al. (2021).

Global Warming Potential

Conventional process to produce Gelatin from bones estimated to release around 9 kg CO₂-eq of emissions (Ma et al., 2019). Gelatin produced from fish waste as feedstock (skin and mechanically separated meat (MSM) residue) has a global warming potential of 43.7 kg CO₂-eq and 85.3 kg CO₂-eq when produced from skin and MSM residue respectively (Sampaio et al, 2017). These life cycle assessments were conducted for the production processes only. The impacts occurred for producing the feedstock is not considered here. The yield from bones is 13.5% indicating the requirement of 7.41 kg of defatted bone to produce 1 kg of gelatin. The yield from skin is 12% and from MSM residue is 3% respectively. The associated impacts should also be included. For reference, sodium polyacrylate (alternative gel) produced from fossil fuels emits 4 kg CO₂-eq for 1kg of gel (Gontia and Janssen, 2016). Clearly, fossil-based alternative performs better in both cases. High emissions for gelatin produced from fish waste could be because of its lower yields augmented by the lab-scale production processes.

Abiotic Resource Depletion

For bone-based gelatin production, non-renewable extraction is 154 MJ primary and mineral extraction is 0.3 MJ surplus (Ma et al., 2019). Metal depletion is 0.775 and 1.7 kg Fe eq, fossil depletion is 8.54 and 16.4 kg oil eq for gelatin production from skin and MSM residue respectively (Sampaio et al, 2017). The units are different due to different impact assessment methods. Values for the alternate gel are currently not available and will be explored in the future.

Toxicity

Fresh water ecotoxicity is 1.09 and 2.09 CTUe, human toxicity – non cancer values are 2.56×10^{-8} and 4.92×10^{-8} CTUh, human toxicity – cancer values are 8.76×10^{-9} and 1.69×10^{-8} CTUh, for gelatin production from skin and MSM residue respectively (Sampaio et al, 2017). Aquatic ecotoxicity is 3.4×10^3 kg TEG water, terrestrial ecotoxicity is 3.43×10^2 kg TEG soil, carcinogens are 0.0841 kg C₂H₃CL eq, and non-carcinogens are 0.238 kg C₂H₃CL eq for gelatin produced from bones (Ma et al., 2019). Toxicity values for the alternate gel are currently not available and will be explored in the future.

Acidification

For production of gelatin from bones, sum of aquatic and terrestrial acidification is given as 0.246 kg SO₂-eq (Ma et al., 2019). Terrestrial acidification potential for gelatin produced from fish wastes is given as 0.06 and 0.16 kg SO₂-eq from skin and MSM residues respectively (Sampaio et al., 2017). The total acidification potential for fossil based alternate gel production is 0.01 kg SO₂-eq (Gontia and Janssen, 2016).

Eutrophication

Fresh water eutrophication values are 5.21×10^{-3} and 3.5×10^{-2} kg P eq, marine eutrophication values are 8.33×10^{-3} and 2.99×10^{-2} kg N eq for gelatin production from skin and MSM residue respectively (Sampaio et al., 2017). Aquatic eutrophication is 2.62×10^{-3} kg PO₄ P-lim for gelatin produced from bones (Ma et al., 2019). Aquatic and terrestrial eutrophication potential of alternate gel production is 4.5×10^{-3} kg PO₄ eq (Gontia and Janssen, 2016).

Biodegradability and micro-Pollution

Gelatin fully degrades within five days (Sreejith et al., 2023). On the other hand, sodium polyacrylate is degradable only by specific microbes under certain conditions (Hayashi et al., 1994). Gelatin highly outperforms the alternate gel in this indicator. When starting the exploration, the main focus has been on biodegradability and as such had taken precedence over other indicators. Once this was established, other environmental and later social and economic sustainability aspects were explored.

Social Sustainability Performance

Most social issues are connected to resources used, region of their origin and production. PSILCA database that supports the assessment of social impacts clearly segregates its inventory based on their origin and production. The main resource for gelatin production is the feedstock from animal sources. The social sustainability performance can be attributed to those impacts associated with animal products. The other main resources include transportation of the feedstock, chemicals used in purification and cleansing of the feedstock, electricity and energy requirements of the production plants (Ma et al., 2019, Sampaio et al, 2017). At this point, we ignore the impacts associated with these resources. Aranda et al. (2021) conducted a social life cycle assessment for pork production in Spain. We consider this to be our reference for social impacts of animal products in Spain.

Supply Chain Working Conditions

Focusing on the meat production, previous studies identified ‘gender diversity’ (only 25% women), ‘gender pay gap’ (15% less for women from their male counterparts), and ‘trade union density’ (only 10% of work force belong to one) were identified to be high risk factors for meat production in Spain (Aranda et al., 2021). The performance in ‘average monthly wages’ was favorable.

Local Community

Performance in terms of ‘healthy living conditions’ and ‘local employment’ was favorable for the conducted assessment in Spain (Aranda et al., 2021).

Society

Performance in the indicators of ‘illiteracy’, ‘certified environmental management systems’, was observed to be good. However, overall contribution to economic development was under performing with ‘public spending on education’ being the risk factor.

Social Acceptance

Since gelatin production involves animal feedstocks, multiple acceptance issues, for example due to disease-related, life-style (e.g. vegan) or religious concerns (Zin et al., 2021). However, fish-based

gelatin has more acceptance both in terms religious as well as disease related concerns (de la Caba et al., 2019). Further, animal welfare concerns could be another barrier for using gelatin from animal sources (Alonso et al., 2020). However, a positive social acceptance is observed when the products are derived from wastes (Russo et al., 2019), in our case, gelatin derived from wastes of food and meat industry.

Economic Sustainability Performance

Economic aspects have not been discussed in much detail for gelatin in the academic literature so far. This could be due to the processes for the production of gelatin have long been established. The current market price of gelatin in North America is at 7510\$/MT (Chemanalyst, 2024). The price of superabsorbent polymer is 1600\$/MT (Chemanalyst, 2024a). However, market prices do not represent the costs of the products. Life cycle costs is a consistent method that considers all cost in a controlled system which would be relevant for comparison. There are other economic studies for gelatin, but the metrics for assessment are not consistent across these studies. Charoenkool et al. (2024) conducted a techno-economic analysis to check the feasibility of producing gelatin from shrimp shell wastes. Indicators chosen here are return on investment and payback period. No details on the product costs provided.

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